

A Deep Learning Fault Diagnose Method for Turbine Bearing: Digital Twin Mechanism

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ABSTRACT:

This study presents a digital twin (DT) based wind turbine bearing fault diagnosis approach to address the issues of insufficient fault sample size and inaccurate diagnosis. To assist in diagnosing bearing faults in wind turbines, a DT system was built. Bearing vibration signal enhancement processing, which is based on the Hilbert-Huang transform, is used to improve the data samples of vibration signals and decrease the noise in these signals. In order to diagnose bearing defects in wind turbines, a convolutional neural network model was trained and tested using data-enhanced samples. The experimental results showed that the suggested method is feasible and effective, increased the stability and accuracy of defect diagnosis in wind turbine bearings, and solved the problem of data augmentation in one-dimensional vibration signals.

Keywords: Digital twin, wind turbine bearing, convolutional neural network, fault diagnosis.

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INTRODUCTION

In today's era, turbine bearing failure detection has become the de facto standard for wind turbine bearings due to its rapid progress. DT technologies [1-3], the internet of things [4], cloud computing [5], and artificial intelligence [6] all have the potential to revolutionize the way bearing faults are presented in turbines. The majority of the current bearing fault diagnosis research uses data-driven methods, such as signal analysis and machine learning [7], to identify bearing faults. The area of fault diagnosis makes extensive use of deep learning due to its powerful feature extraction capabilities.

He et al., [8] used bearing vibration signals to establish a deep learning model of mixed depth signals to effectively solve the problem of bearing fault diagnosis. Zhu et al., [9] introduced the Nesterov momentum method to adaptively optimize the learning rate of the deep belief network, speed up the training of the network model, and then realize bearing fault diagnosis. Islam et al., [10] used wavelet envelope transform to adaptively decompose the vibration signal of bearing fault, and established a deep convolutional neural network (CNN) to extract the time-frequency fault characteristics of bearing fault. This method combines feature extraction with fault classifications are integrated to achieve intelligent diagnosis of bearing faults.

In order to solve the problems of few bearing fault samples and category imbalance in actual working conditions, Xu et al., [11] proposed a bearing fault diagnosis method based on secondary data enhancement and deep convolution network. The proposed method is used to improving the utilization rate of samples and significantly improved the bearing quality. Fault diagnosis efficiency and accuracy. At the same time, Ren et al., [12] proposed a data enhancement strategy to expand the diversity of training samples, use enhanced samples to train the convolutional neural network model, and improve the reliability of fault diagnosis when samples are scarce.

Considering the specific features of wind turbine bearing failures, Yan et al., [13] employed the mutual information technique to examine the attributes that have a strong correlation with the temperature of the gearbox bearing. They subsequently developed a long-short-term memory neural network deep learning model to forecast the temperature of the wind turbine gearbox bearing. This model successfully enables the timely detection of bearing failure by issuing real-time warnings. Huang et al., [14] proposed a BP neural network optimized by the particle SWARM algorithm. Using the gearbox temperature parameters as input features, the bearing temperature was predicted through the BP neural network, and the wind turbine fault alarm or alarm threshold was analyzed to achieve early warning of gearbox faults. Chen et al., [15] used Fourier transform to increase the significance sequence of rolling bearing vibration signals, which improved the accuracy of bearing fault diagnosis and reduced the training time of the diagnostic model.

With the development of the new generation of information technology, DT technology provides new solutions for the intelligent management of complex equipment. Research on DT technology in robotics [16], intelligent battery [17] and power equipment [18] has achieved some preliminary results. This paper uses DT technology to build a wind turbines twin. Based on the twin data of wind turbines. Hilbert-Huang transform (HHT) is used to enhance the wind turbine bearing fault sample data. The objective is to construct a network model for diagnosing bearing faults using CNN. This model will be trained using historical data on wind turbine bearing faults. The aim is to enable intelligent diagnosis of different bearing failure patterns and their respective causes.

DIGITAL TWIN SYSTEM FOR WIND TURBINES

Referring to the framework of the DT system of the Energy Internet [19] and the five-dimensional model framework of the DT [20], the framework of the DT system for wind turbines is shown in Figure 1, and the system architecture consists of four layers: the physical layer, the data layer, the model layer, and the service layer.

Figure 1. Digital Twin System Framework for Wind Turbines

Physical Layer

The physical layer includes physical equipment such as wind turbine equipment and sensing equipment. By deploying various sensors to collect information related to the operation of wind turbines, the collected data mainly includes unit parameters, environmental information, power grid information, rotational speed information, temperature information, vibration information, setting parameters, time information, pitch information, etc. The coding and identification of each physical equipment of the wind turbine uses technologies such as laser marking machines, metal barcodes/QR codes, and RFID to establish equipment identification rules to meet the association mapping between physical equipment and data.

In order to meet the real-time processing efficiency of massive data and reduce cloud data redundancy, the data collection terminal uses intelligent gateways and controllers with edge processing capabilities to implement data preprocessing at the edge. Among them, the edge cleans, processes, preprocesses and stores the original collected data; the cloud receives and stores high-quality, low-redundant data processed by the edge, and combines the mechanisms through data sharing, data analysis, data mining, etc.

Data Layer

The data layer includes three parts: data transmission, data processing and data center. Among them, data transmission involves equipment communication protocols, data transmission methods, etc. For example, smart gateways/controllers use Modbus protocol to communicate with various sensors to achieve various data collection. Data processing uses edge devices to perform format conversion, correlation analysis, processing, cleaning, abnormal data processing, etc. on the original collected data, and then transmits the processed data to the cloud server data center through TCP/IP and UDP protocols. Data center relational databases can include MySQL, SQL Server, PostgreSQL, etc., and non-relational databases can include HBase, Mongo-Db, Redis, etc.

Model Layer

The model layer contains the three-dimensional twin model and mechanism model of the wind turbine. Among them, the three-dimensional twin model of the wind turbine is a mirror mapping of the physical entity of the wind turbine. It has functions such as assembly constraints between components and simulated motion. It can be created through CAD modeling software, Unity-3D fast scanner, etc. The mechanism model includes the working principle of wind turbines, HHT model, CNN network, HHT-CNN bearing fault diagnosis model, etc.

Service Layers

The service layer includes web applications with functions such as wind turbine management, fault diagnosis, abnormality warning, and management decision-making. Mainly using Vue, HTML5, CSS, JavaScript, WebGL, Unity-3D, C #, MQTT and other technologies. Driven by twin data, the HHT-CNN network model is used to realize real-time diagnosis of wind turbine bearing faults.

CNN BASED WIND BEARING FAULT DIAGNOSIS

CNN Model Construction

CNN can enhance the data's feature extraction capability by utilizing convolution and pooling techniques. The neurons within the layers of a CNN employ local connections and weight sharing. This technique significantly reduces the number of model parameters, resulting in faster and more efficient model calculations and training. CNN exhibits strong fault tolerance, parallel processing, and self-learning capabilities, enabling it to handle samples with faults and distortions [21]. A one-dimensional CNN is chosen to train and analyze wind turbine bearing fault vibration samples, as the vibration signal from the bearing is one-dimensional data. This approach enables accurate diagnosis of bearing faults.

Convolutional layer: Contains a convolution kernel. Through the convolution operation of the convolution kernel, multiple convolution feature maps are obtained, and the features of the original input data are extracted to obtain more abstract features. Local connections between layers and weight sharing allow key information to be filtered and retained, thereby reducing the size of the data and the amount of computation. The convolution operation can be expressed as:

$$y^{l(i,j)} = K_i^l * x^{l(j)} = \sum_{j'=0}^{c-1} K_i^{l(j')} x^{l(j+j')} \quad (1)$$

where, $K_i^{l(j')}$ is the j' weight in the i^{th} convolution kernel of the j^{th} layer; $x^{l(j+j')}$ is the j convolved local area in the l layer with j' weight-sensing position. The c is the size of the convolution kernel.

Pooling layer: The local features obtained by convolution are down-sampled and are not modified by reverse broadcasting. Through the feature compression of the pooling layer, the dimensionality of the feature matrix can be reduced, which can greatly reduce the parameters of model training to obtain the main features, optimize the network and improve the efficiency of model training to a certain extent. Commonly used pooling operations include maximum pooling, average pooling, random pooling, overlapping pooling, etc. Among them, the maximum pooling operation is to use

the maximum value of the sensing area in the pooling layer as the output of the pooling layer. The formula is expressed as:

$$p^{l(i,t)} = \text{mix}_{(j-1)c+1 \leq t \leq jw}(a^{l(i,t)}) \quad (2)$$

where, $a^{l(i,t)}$ is the t activation value of the i^{th} feature map in the l layer.

Fault Diagnosis Process Based on CNN

The wind turbine bearing vibration signal is preprocessed by HHT to achieve data enhancement of the training samples. Combined with the strong feature extraction and learning capabilities of CNN, automatic feature extraction and diagnosis of training samples can be achieved. The fault diagnosis process of wind turbine bearings based on CNN is shown in Figure 2. The process mainly consists of three stages: data preprocessing, model construction and training, and sample testing.

Figure 2. Fault Diagnosis Process of Wind Turbine Bearings Based on CNN

Data preprocessing: First, the vibration signal is normalized, and then the training samples and test samples are selected in a ratio of 2:1. The bearing vibration signal data is processed based on HHT according to Section 2 to enhance the vibration signal characteristics and reduce noise interference.

Model construction and training: First, the convolution and pooling of CNN are constructed, and the parameters are initialized and set; then the CNN network is trained through training samples until the iterative convergence is completed, and the training of the CNN model is completed.

Sample testing: Input the selected bearing fault samples to the trained CNN model, the model output's fault prediction results, compares the prediction results with the actual results of the sample, and analyzes the CNN network bearing fault diagnosis accuracy. In addition, under the DT system, real-time diagnosis and analysis of bearing vibration data collected in real time are performed on wind turbine equipment to achieve real-time diagnosis of bearing faults.

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATIONS

Experimental Data

The Case Western Reserve University bearing experimental data set is used to verify the effectiveness and feasibility of the proposed method. The experimental object is a high-speed rolling bearing of a wind turbine gearbox, model SKF6025-2RS. The vibration data of the drive-end bearing under normal conditions, roller failure, inner ring failure and outer ring failure were taken as samples. The fault sample information is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Fault Sample Information

Fault type	Fault diameter/mil	mark
Inner ring	7	1
	14	2
	21	3
Outer ring	1	4
	14	5
	21	6
Roller element	7	7
	14	8
	21	9
Normal	0	10

The number of samples is 1,000, the sampling frequency is 12 k Hz, the bearing speed is 1,796 r/min, and the number of sampling points for each sample is 6,000. Figure 3 shows the time domain diagram of vibration signals of four types of bearing faults, in which the spectrum is the time domain after HHT processing. It can be seen from Figures 3 that after HHT enhancement processing, the bearing vibration signal has obvious characteristics, reducing noise interference and enhancing sample characteristics.

Figure 3. Time Domain Diagram of the Bearing Vibration Signal Under Normal Condition, as Well as Inner Ring, Outer Ring, and Rolling Element Faults

Result Verification

The parameters of the constructed CNN network model for bearing fault diagnosis are shown in Table 2. The CNN network consists of 2 convolutional layers and 2 pooling layers. The samples before and after HHT processing were used to train and test the CNN network, and the bearing fault diagnosis results were analyzed and compared. Through multiple experimental comparisons, the fault diagnosis accuracy of the two samples can be obtained, as shown in Figure 4. It can be seen from the figure that the bearing fault diagnosis accuracy of the HHT enhanced sample is generally higher than that of the original sample.

Table 2. CNN Model Structural Parameters

Network structure	parameter name	Parameter value
Convolution layer	Number of layers	2
	The number of convolution kernels in the first convolutional layer	16
	The size of the convolution kernel of the first convolutional layer	3×3
	The number of convolution kernels in the second convolutional layer	32
	The second convolutional layer convolution kernel size	3×3
Pooling layer	Number of layers	2
	Layer 1 pooling kernel size	2×2
	Layer 2 pooling kernel size	2×2

Figure 4 Comparison of Diagnostic Accuracy Between Original and HHT Enhanced Samples

In order to more clearly and conveniently observe the bearing fault diagnosis effect under the condition of unbalanced fault categories, the experiment uses a separate test set for verification. The number of samples in the four major categories in the test set is 150 each, with a total of 600 samples. A single sample contains 6,000 sampling points. By comparing the fault diagnosis results of the test samples with the real marks, the fault diagnosis accuracy of different bearing fault samples is compared, as shown in Table 3. In addition, in order to further verify the effectiveness and superiority of the proposed method, a comparison was made with the method in reference [6]. The comparison

of fault diagnosis accuracy for different test datasets is shown in Figure 5. From the figure, it can be seen that the overall accuracy of bearing fault diagnosis in the proposed method is higher than that in reference [6], and the diagnostic accuracy is relatively stable.

Table 3. Fault Diagnosis Accuracy Rate of Different Bearing Fault Samples

Test sets	data	Inner fault	ring	Outer fault	ring	Roller element fault	Normal	Average
1		98.26		94.27		89.25	100	95.45
2		97.34		93.09		93.01	100	95.86
3		94.26		95.28		90.34	97.9	94.45
4		97.11		94.89		88.67	100	95.17
5		98.47		95.11		90.12	98.56	95.57
6		96.46		94.56		88.54	100	94.89
7		97.83		94.87		92.12	100	96.21
8		96.78		93.56		91.54	98.26	95.04

Figure 5. Comparison of Accuracy in Bearing Fault Diagnosis

For wind turbine DT, a system has been applied in the operation and maintenance management of wind turbines in a wind. There are real wind turbine bearing fault data in the twin data. The wind turbine bearing fault data set is obtained by processing the bearing fault information. The fault data sets of wind turbine bearings No. 22 and 23 were selected as test objects to further verify the bearing fault diagnosis model based on HHT-CNN. Due to time span limitations, there are few bearing fault data in actual operation of wind turbines. The number of inner ring faults, rolling body faults, and outer ring faults were selected to be 23, 19, and 15 respectively.

CONCLUSION

In order to effectively improve the efficiency and accuracy of wind turbine bearing fault diagnosis, a wind turbine bearing fault diagnosis method based on DT is proposed, and a wind turbine DT system is constructed, which provides a platform and data source for real-time diagnosis of wind turbine bearing faults. The bearing vibration signal data enhancement processing method based on HHT solves the problem of sparseness and noise of wind turbine bearing fault samples and increases the diversity and characteristics of the samples. On this basis, the bearing fault diagnosis model based

on CNN uses the vibration signals enhanced by HHT as model training samples, which improves the accuracy and stability of the diagnosis model. Compared with the direct input of bearing original signal samples, the accuracy of bearing fault diagnosis based on HHT-CNN is improved by about 2.5%. In the DT environment, the twin data of the wind turbine bearing operation can be obtained in real time. Combined with the three-dimensional visualization of the wind turbine, the operation monitoring and fault diagnosis of the wind turbine bearing can be realized more intuitively, accurately and efficiently. Follow-up work will focus on further research on the remaining life prediction of wind turbine bearings.

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REFERENCES

1. M.U. Shoukat, S. Yu, S. Shi, Y. Li, J. Yu, "Evaluate the connected autonomous vehicles infrastructure using digital twin model based on cyber-physical combination of intelligent network," *In 2021 5th CAA International Conference on Vehicular Control and Intelligence (CVCI)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE, 2021. DOI: [10.1109/CVCI54083.2021.9661190](https://doi.org/10.1109/CVCI54083.2021.9661190)
2. M.U. Shoukat, L. Yan, J. Zhang, Y. Cheng, M.U. Raza, A. Niaz, "Smart home for enhanced healthcare: exploring human machine interface oriented digital twin model," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, pp. 1-19, 2023. DOI: [10.1007/s11042-023-16875-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-16875-9)
3. M.U. Shoukat, L. Yan, W. Liu, F. Hussain, S.A. Nawaz, A. Niaz, "Digital Twin-Driven Virtual Control Technology of Home-Use Robot: Human-Cyber-Physical System," *In 2022 17th International Conference on Emerging Technologies (ICET)* (pp. 240-246). IEEE, 2022. DOI: [10.1109/ICET56601.2022.10004685](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICET56601.2022.10004685)
4. A. Niaz, S. Khan, F. Niaz, M.U. Shoukat, I. Niaz, J. Yanbing, "Smart City IoT Application for Road Infrastructure Safety and Monitoring by Using Digital Twin," *In 2022 International Conference on IT and Industrial Technologies (ICIT)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE, 2022. DOI: [10.1109/ICIT56493.2022.9989141](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIT56493.2022.9989141)
5. Z. Zeeshan, U.A. Bhatti, W.H. Memon, S. Ali, S.A. Nawaz, M.M. Nizamani, M.U. Shoukat, "Feature-based multi-criteria recommendation system using a weighted approach with ranking correlation," *Intelligent Data Analysis*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 1013-1029, 2022. DOI: [10.3233/IDA-205388](https://doi.org/10.3233/IDA-205388)
6. S.A. Nawaz, J. Li, U.A. Bhatti, M.U. Shoukat, R.M. Ahmad, "AI-based object detection latest trends in remote sensing, multimedia and agriculture applications," *Frontiers in Plant Science*, vol. 13, id. 1041514, 2022. DOI: [10.3389/fpls.2022.1041514](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.1041514)
7. Y. Pan, H. Wang, J. Chen, R. Hong, "Fault recognition of large-size low-speed slewing bearing based on improved deep belief network," *Journal of Vibration and Control*, vol. 29, no. 11-12, pp. 2829-2841, 2023. DOI: [10.1177/10775463221085856](https://doi.org/10.1177/10775463221085856)
8. M. He, D. He, "A new hybrid deep signal processing approach for bearing fault diagnosis using vibration signals," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 396, pp. 542-555, 2020. DOI: [10.1016/j.neucom.2018.12.088](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2018.12.088)
9. Z. Zhu, Y. Lei, G. Qi, Y. Chai, N. Mazur, Y. An, X. Huang, "A review of the application of deep learning in intelligent fault diagnosis of rotating machinery," *Measurement*, vol. 206, id. 112346, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.measurement.2022.112346](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2022.112346)
10. M. M. Islam, J.M. Kim, "Automated bearing fault diagnosis scheme using 2D representation of wavelet packet transform and deep convolutional neural network," *Computers in Industry*, vol. 106, pp. 142-153, 2019. DOI: [10.1016/j.compind.2019.01.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2019.01.008)

11. G. Xu, M. Liu, Z. Jiang, D. Söffker, W. Shen, "Bearing fault diagnosis method based on deep convolutional neural network and random forest ensemble learning," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 5, id. 1088, 2019. DOI: [10.3390/s19051088](https://doi.org/10.3390/s19051088)
12. Z. Ren, D. Gao, Y. Zhu, Q. Ni, K. Yan, J. Hong, "Generative adversarial networks driven by multi-domain information for improving the quality of generated samples in fault diagnosis," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 124, id. 106542, 2023. DOI: [10.1016/j.engappai.2023.106542](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2023.106542)
13. G. Yan, C. Yu, Y. Bai, "Wind turbine bearing temperature forecasting using a new data-driven ensemble approach," *Machines*, vol. 9, no. 11, id. 248, 2021. DOI: [10.3390/machines9110248](https://doi.org/10.3390/machines9110248)
14. M. Huang, Z. Liu, Y. Tao, "Mechanical fault diagnosis and prediction in IoT based on multi-source sensing data fusion," *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory*, vol. 102, id. 101981, 2020. DOI: [10.1016/j.simpat.2019.101981](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpat.2019.101981)
15. Z. Chen, Y. Yang, C. He, Y. Liu, X. Liu, Z. Cao, "Feature extraction based on hierarchical improved envelope spectrum entropy for rolling bearing fault diagnosis," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 2023. DOI: [10.1109/TIM.2023.3277938](https://doi.org/10.1109/TIM.2023.3277938)
16. M.U. Shoukat, L. Yan, D. Deng, M. Imtiaz, M. Safdar, S.A. Nawaz, "Cognitive robotics: Deep learning approaches for trajectory and motion control in complex environment.," *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, vol. 60, id. 102370, 2024. DOI: [10.1016/j.aei.2024.102370](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2024.102370)
17. M.U. Shoukat, L. Yan, C. Du, M.U.M. Raza, M. Adeel, T. Khan, "Application of Digital Twin in Smart Battery Electric Vehicle: Industry 4.0," *In 2022 International Conference on IT and Industrial Technologies (ICIT)* (pp. 1-7). IEEE, 2022. DOI: [10.1109/ICIT56493.2022.9989044](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIT56493.2022.9989044)
18. M.Q. Habib, M.U. Shoukat, M. Irfan, M. Zubair, S. Ahmed, M. Raza, A. Sarwar, "Smart Meter Development Using Digital Twin Technology for Green Energy Distribution Optimization," *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 181-190, 2023. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(3\).20](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(3).20)
19. W. Huang, Y. Zhang, W. Zeng, "Development and application of digital twin technology for integrated regional energy systems in smart cities," *Sustainable Computing: Informatics and Systems*, vol. 36, id. 100781, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.suscom.2022.100781](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.suscom.2022.100781)
20. S.R. Newrzella, D.W. Franklin, S. Haider, "5-dimension cross-industry digital twin applications model and analysis of digital twin classification terms and models," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 131306-131321, 2021. DOI: [10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3115055](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3115055)
21. A. Sivapriya, N. Kalaiarasi, R. Verma, B. Chokkalingam, J.L. Munda, "Fault Diagnosis of Cascaded Multilevel Inverter Using Multiscale Kernel Convolutional Neural Network," *IEEE Access*, 2023. DOI: [10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3299852](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3299852)

